

A Novel Signal Modeling Method Using the Wavelet Transform.

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ABSTRACT : This paper presents a novel methodology for improving the modeling of non-smooth signals, based on the wavelet transform and neural network function approximation techniques. It is suggested that the enhanced time frequency localization properties of the wavelet transform could provide the means for extracting highly informative features for signal modeling tasks, especially for very spiky signals. These features are used as inputs to neural network nonlinear regression models of the MLP (MultiLayer Perceptron) type in addition to the usually used current and past signal values organized in sliding windows. While the majority of contemporary research efforts to improve the generalization capability of function approximation and classification techniques, like neural networks, employ the reduction of the number of effective parameters, it is demonstrated here that significant improvements in the generalization capability could be achieved by introducing additive informative features. Although our methodology involves an increase of the input space dimensionality it is exhibited, through extensive experimentation, that it leads to significantly better signal modeling of non-smooth peaked signals.

Keywords : neural networks, wavelets, signal modeling, multiresolution analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Information processing of signals has become an essential part of contemporary scientific and developmental activity in the field of computer science and engineering. It is used in telecommunications, in diagnostic systems, in the transmission and analysis of biomedical signals and in time series forecasting among many important disciplines of computer aided engineering. Signal modeling in particular is one of its major targets that plays an integral role in numerous applications. For instance, medical diagnosis involves biomedical signal modeling aiming at extracting important information that characterizes a patient, telecommunications and data transmission employ signal modeling to achieve effective data compression and time series forecasting needs signal modeling for predicting signal fluctuations in time. All these applications involve the analysis and interpretation of complex time series which, in general, can be characterized and represented by non smooth and highly irregular signals.

Therefore, the desired properties of robust signal modeling include the accurate analysis and efficient coding of the delicate oscillations or fluctuations as a function of time or space. These characteristics are essential since the information contained in signals is effectively present in the complicated arabesques appearing in their representations. Thus, anomalies and discontinuities play an instrumental role in signal representation and characterization since they convey important information about fluctuations in time or space. The majority of the above mentioned applications

involve in one way or another the detection and prediction of such anomalies. For instance, medical diagnosis involves peak detection and representation (NMR etc.), while time series forecasting involves modeling and prediction of abnormal variations. The goal of this paper can be summarized as an attempt to achieve robust modeling of signals with irregularities by suggesting a novel methodology involving neural networks and the wavelet signal decomposition.

The various methodologies, which have, so far, been developed for accomplishing successful signal representation, mainly come from linear system theory (Kailath, 1980), stochastic process theory (Papoulis, 1991), the black-box methodology (Juditski, & Zhang, et al., 1994) and dynamical systems analysis (Kaplan, & Glass, 1995). The approach adopted here is based on the black-box methodology and more specifically on neural networks function approximation techniques of the MLP type. It has been proved that these feedforward neural networks are universal function approximators for any continuous and regular function (Hornik, Stinchcombe, & White, 1989). It is demonstrated here that the efficiency of such powerful continuous function modeling techniques can be significantly increased when attempting to represent highly irregular functions (signals) by using the wavelet analysis tools. Thus, the main contribution of this paper is the experimental illustration of the fact that the wavelet signal decomposition can provide the means for extending the function approximation capabilities of MLP in the case of irregular functions.

The rationale underlying the application of the wavelet signal decomposition techniques to such a task is that wavelets offer a successful time-frequency signal representation for enhanced information localization and thus, detection of abnormal fluctuations and signal irregularities as it is described in the next section. One of the contributions of this paper is the experimental demonstration of the ability of the wavelet transform to efficiently model signal abnormalities and represent them in a suitable manner for MLP. It might be supposed that this latter representation should be smooth because such a conjecture could be the only explanation for the improved performance of the MLP Feedforward Neural Networks in the modeling of irregular signals and functions, since their function approximation capabilities theoretically apply only to smooth functions.

This paper, also, shows that the integration of Neural Network and Wavelet techniques is a very promising strategy for solving signal representation tasks. The proposed methodology involves an increase in the input space dimensionality, while the majority of the other MLP generalization improvement techniques attempt to decrease the number of effective parameters as reviewed in the next paragraph. Thus, an important contribution of this paper is the experimental illustration of the efficiency of a novel strategy for improving MLP generalization performance, which can be characterized by the investigation of new informative features to be added to the initial input vectors.

Since the resurgence of interest in Neural information processing research and especially in feedforward networks like MLP, a multitude of methodologies have been proposed for improving their generalization capabilities. The most important of them can be classified as follows.

1. The weight sharing approach, where it is attempted to build suitable kinds of invariance in the network structure (Haykin, 1994).
2. Weight pruning and elimination techniques, like Weigend's method (Weigend, Rumelhart, & Huberman, 1990), which involve the optimization of an appropriate

penalty function in addition to the minimization of the normally used sum of squares error function.

3. Input feature selection and dimensionality reduction techniques, like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) methods (Haykin, 1994).

All the above mentioned approaches attempt to improve neural network generalization capabilities through reducing the number of their effective parameters. Such an approach comes directly from statistics and is related to concepts like the minimum description length (Rissanen, J.) as well as to function approximation methods using polynomials. The methodology suggested here, however, attempts to achieve the same goal by actively seeking for additional informative effective parameters.

Section II summarizes the characteristics of the wavelet transform, which are relevant to this research effort. In the sections III and IV a detailed description of the proposed methodology is offered. Section V shows the promising results obtained through extensive experimentation and finally, section VI concludes the paper and states the future trends of our approach.

2. FEATURE EXTRACTION IN THE WAVELET DOMAIN FOR ENHANCED SIGNAL REPRESENTATION

This section along with the section 3 describes the components of the proposed approach for improving the information processing of irregular signals.

Wavelets offer a general mathematical approach for hierarchical function decomposition. According to this transformation, a function, which can represent an image, a curve, a signal etc., can be described in terms of a coarse level and additive details that range from broad to narrow scales. Wavelets offer a novel technique for computing the levels of detail present, under a framework that is based on a chain of *approximation* vector spaces $\{V_j \subset L^2(\mathcal{R}^2), j \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ and a *scaling* function f such that the set of functions $\{2^{-j/2} f(2^{-j}t - k): k \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ form an orthonormal basis for V_j . These two components introduce a mathematical framework presented by Mallat (Mallat, 1989) and called multiresolution analysis.

The wavelet transform is the correlation between a function and the dilated wavelets (Poularikas, 1996). For a given scale, the wavelet transform is performed with a wavelet transform filter in the Fourier domain, whose impulse response is the scaled wavelet. When the scale is small the wavelet is concentrated in time and the wavelet analysis has a detailed view of the signal. When the scale increases the wavelet becomes spread out in time and the wavelet analysis takes into account the long-time behavior of the signal.

The dilation of the wavelets permit the wavelet analysis to zoom in on discontinuities, singularities and edges and to zoom out for a global view. This is a unique property of the wavelet transform, important for non-stationary and non-transitional signal analysis. Multiresolution analysis divides the signal into different frequency bands. In each band the signal is analysed with a resolution matched to the scales of the wavelets. Therefore, the wavelet transform is a local operator in both time and frequency domains.

Two are the main stages of the suggested novel methodology. The first one deals with the extraction of suitable and informative features from the signal, while the second one copes with its modeling viewed as a function approximation task based on the previously selected features.

Concerning the feature extraction stage, main stream techniques in signal modeling use features extracted from either time or spectral domain (Hamilton, 1994). Regarding the latter approach, the majority of research efforts in this area of signal processing have mainly employed the Fourier spectrum in order to select informative features. Since the explosion of interest in the applications of the wavelet transform, very little research work has been conducted with similar goals, despite the improved time-frequency and localization properties of this transform depicted in section II. This paper investigates the use of the wavelet transform in extracting informative features for enhanced signal modeling thus, attempting to fill in this gap.

One of the novelties suggested here is the fusion of the original signal data and the coefficients of their corresponding DWT (Discrete Wavelet Transform) multiresolution analysis for achieving improved solutions through treating these data as input patterns to the MLP function approximation module described in the next section. While contemporary time domain signal modeling methods involve present along with past sampled signal values as input features, new additional informative features are actively sought here in the wavelet domain. The optimal features extracted from this domain and herein proposed for improved modeling of irregular signals are the wavelet coefficients associated with a subset of the channels as explained next. This procedure for selecting wavelet channels and thus, coefficients, that is next analyzed is another novelty of this work regarding feature extraction and selection. Moreover, there is no, so far, attempt in the literature for investigating the use of the wavelet coefficients as input patterns in function approximation techniques for signal modeling problems.

Therefore, the task of abnormal fluctuation modeling-prediction is considered in both the time and the wavelet domain so as to exploit the signal representation capabilities of the wavelet transform stated in section II and (Freeman, 1995). Besides, in this way we could exploit the well known local information extraction properties of the wavelet signal decomposition as well as the well known features of wavelet denoising (Donoho, & Johnstone, 1994). We, respectively, use the popular 1-D discrete wavelet transform schemes (Meyer, 1993; Kolaczyk, 1994; etc.) in order to obtain the wavelet analysis of the original signals containing abnormal fluctuations. It is expected that signal anomalies, considered in the wavelet domain, should obtain smooth representations but due to the enhanced time-frequency localization properties of the wavelet transform, these abnormal fluctuations, whose statistics vary from the ones of the signal background, should more or less clearly emerge in the wavelet bands foreground. We have experimented with the standard one-level 1-D wavelet transform using nearly all the well known bases like Haar, Daubechies, Coiflet, Symmlet etc. However, and this is very interesting, regarding the one level DWT signal decomposition, only the 1-D Haar transform has exhibited the expected and desired properties. All its other formations based on orthonormal, continuous and compactly supported bases result in such smooth signal representations that the abnormal fluctuations do not appear in the bands. Since we have performed a one-level wavelet decomposition of the signals, we have obtained two main wavelet channels. The first one corresponds to a low-pass filtered version of the original signal, while the second

one corresponds to a high-pass filtered version of it. A lot of experimentation has revealed a fact that could be anticipated. To be more specific, the first channel represents such a smooth version of the original signal that the abnormalities do not appear at all. On the other hand, these irregularities clearly emerge in the second channel. Therefore, the second band of the detailed wavelet coefficients has been selected for further processing, as the most relevant for abnormalities modeling.

After discussing the main concepts involved in the suggested feature extraction methodology, it is next described in detail.

- **Step 1** The signal, consisted of N samples, is successively scanned by sliding windows of length M . Therefore, each such window contains M samples.

- **Step 2** For each sliding window, the one-level 1-D Haar DWT is applied to the corresponding set of M signal samples and results in obtaining two bands. Namely, the channels of approximation and detail coefficients respectively.

- **Step 3** Subsequently, the second band of detail coefficients is extracted from the wavelet transformed original signal, according to the previous discussion and thus, $M/2$ wavelet coefficients are obtained.

- **Step 4** Therefore, for each sliding window, a vector of $M+M/2$ components could be formed, consisting of the M associated signal samples plus their corresponding $M/2$ detail wavelet coefficients. Each such vector is used for constructing an input pattern in the function approximation stage of the proposed approach, depicted in the next section.

- **Step 5** Finally, we define a two-component vector for each such input pattern. This vector comprises the two future signal values corresponding to the set of M samples of the associated sliding window. These two values should be predicted by the function approximation module, given the corresponding input pattern previously determined, thus, forming the desired output vector.

Having completely described the feature extraction stage, we can proceed by defining the Neural network module for modeling irregular signals.

3. THE NEURAL NETWORK PROPOSED SOLUTION FOR MODELING IRREGULAR SIGNALS

The function approximation capabilities of MLP mentioned in section I, justify its use in the second stage of the system, although other important function approximation methods, like MARS (Cherkassky, Friedman, & Wechsler, 1994), might have equally well been utilized. To be more specific about the relation between function approximation and signal modeling, it should be pointed out that the purpose of any signal modeling method is to, either analytically or by using well defined algorithmic procedures, state the model that associates future, present and past signal values. Therefore, the goal of the second stage of the proposed approach is to find the analytical or algorithmic procedure that gives the future values of the signal from its present and past values. It is obvious that this problem can be stated as a function approximation task. Neural Networks, like MLP, as well as the other techniques belonging to the black-box signal modeling methodology solve it in an algorithmic and not analytical way.

The function approximation module of the suggested approach utilizes neural networks of the MLP type for modeling signals with abnormal fluctuations. These feedforward networks are trained and tested using the patterns extracted by employing

the previously analyzed procedure. Their architecture involves an input layer consisting of $M+M/2$ inputs, one or two hidden layers with varying number of processing elements and an output layer consisting of two outputs. Contrary to the previous research attempts for improving generalization capabilities of MLP, as mentioned above, an increase in the input space dimensionality can be obviously noticed here. Namely, instead of the usually employed past and present M signal values as inputs to the methods involved in similar problems, their corresponding $M/2$ detailed wavelet coefficients are used as additional informative inputs to MLP, imposing a very important positive effect on its function approximation capabilities, as it is shown in the next section. Moreover, instead of having only one signal value as output to the MLP module, as it is usually encountered in similar research efforts, two future signal values are involved in our approach so as to consider the more than one output effect on MLP prediction and function approximation in general performance, which has not been faced so far in detail. The many outputs effect on MLP generalization capability has been experimentally investigated, although not too thoroughly, only in the case of classification problems, where the conclusion is that when the number of classes is large then MLP classification accuracy diminishes (Anond, Mehrotra, Mohan, & Ranka, 1995).

The inputs to the networks as well as their desired outputs in the training and test phase are derived by normalizing all the features previously extracted in the first stage of the proposed methodology by the formula :

$$X_{norm} = \frac{(X - X_{min})}{(X_{max} - X_{min})}$$

where, X is an original input or desired output feature, X_{norm} is the corresponding normalized feature and X_{max} , X_{min} the maximum and minimum values of X , respectively.

We have used the on-line backpropagation algorithm for training the MLP employed in this function approximation stage. Although much more sophisticated training techniques could have been involved, we have utilized this simple but efficient algorithm since our purpose was mainly to evaluate the effect of the suggested feature extraction methodology on MLP generalization capabilities.

4. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

We have conducted an extensive experimental investigation in order to demonstrate the efficiency of our signal modeling methodology in improving the function approximation performance of MLP. To this end, we have attempted to apply our approach to the three highly irregular signals shown in Figures 1-3 respectively. These signals are not artificial. They have been extracted, instead, from three 1024 X 1024 images downloaded from the Internet and showing complex scenes. To be more specific, each such signal was a row, randomly selected, from a 1024 X 1024 matrix of pixel intensities corresponding to the image associated with this signal. This procedure ensures that the three signals involved in our study are not special and, on the other hand, they are irregular. This latter property holds despite the well known fact that local image statistics, in real world pictures as the ones herein selected, do not vary too much. The smooth variations of image statistics, however, occur only when 2-D

neighborhoods are considered, which is the usual case in image processing. Thus, by following the previously mentioned row selection procedure, which disregards the 2-D nature of natural images, we have constructed three non-smooth and truly irregular signals.

Figure 1. Original Signal 1

Figure 2. Original Signal 2

Figure 3. Original Signal 3

Each of the three signals, Figures 1-3, contains 1024 samples and therefore, $N=1024$. The length of the sliding window scanning these signals has been selected to be $M=32$, after experimentation. We have found that at this window size the signal corresponding

to the detailed 1-D Haar wavelet coefficients, associated with the high-pass filtered version of the original M samples, starts to faithfully represent signal abnormalities.

Therefore, the neural networks of the MLP type involved in this study have the following architectures. The simple input MLP, whose generalization performance is attempted to be improved, has $M=32$ inputs. On the other hand, the MLP with the enhanced feature vector, following our feature extraction methodology, has 48 inputs. Both the simple and enhanced input MLP have 2 outputs as described in the previous section. The patterns extracted as depicted in sections III-IV have been organized in training, validation and test sets, according to the 6 experiments attempted for each of the two above mentioned MLPs (two experiments for each signal), as explained in the next paragraph. After a lot of experimentation, it was found that two hidden layers result in better function approximation accuracy for both MLP. The best architectures employed in our experiments were the 32-30-30-2 for the simple MLP and the 48-35-35-2 for the enhanced input MLP, although many other networks have, also, given similar results. In addition, their learning rate and momentum coefficients have been selected so as to achieve for each MLP best average performance concerning the six validation sets corresponding to its six associated experiments explained in the next paragraph. It was found that, for both MLPs, these best coefficients were 0.4 and 0.5 respectively.

Four specific experiments have been conducted for each such irregular signal. In the first and the second of them we consider the 90% of the total number of patterns constructed from the corresponding signal as known to either MLP mentioned above and the rest as unknown. On the contrary, in the third and the fourth experiment we consider the 70% of the total number of patterns as known and the rest as unknown. In either case, the training set and the validation set have as their union the set of the known to the models patterns, while the test set is equivalent to the full set of patterns. The set of the known to the MLPs patterns is randomly selected from the complete set of patterns corresponding to the associated signal, which, since each such signal consists of 1024 samples and the scanning window is of length 32, equals to 991. Moreover, the training set comprises the 90% of the known patterns, while the validation one comprises the rest 10% and it has been used for aiding the selection of the best learning parameters in both MLP, as discussed above. The dimensionality of the training, validation and test patterns depends on the MLP utilized. More specifically, the first and the third experimental attempts involve the simple input MLP, while the second and the fourth ones the enhanced input MLP. Therefore, the former group of these experiments employs pattern pairs of the type (32 inputs, 2 desired outputs) while the latter one of the type (48 inputs, 2 desired outputs). At this point we should mention that the above depicted type of data organization clearly results in that all the 12 problems assigned to the two MLPs cannot be characterized as purely extrapolation tasks but as tasks involving both prediction and interpolation concepts in a joined fashion. All the results regarding the performance of simple and enhanced input MLP in their training and test sets are shown in Table 1 and Figures 4-21.

From Table 1, it is obvious that the augmented input vector MLP clearly and consistently outperforms the simple input vector MLP regarding signal modeling capabilities, for all the experiments attempted. Their signal modeling accuracy is evaluated in the test phase by separately considering the two sums of squared errors

corresponding to the prediction of the first and the second future point, respectively, given the M samples belonging to the associated sliding window of the test set.

A careful comparison of the reconstructed signals, shown in Figures 4-5, discloses the superiority of the DWT augmented input vector MLP as regards peak detection.

Figure 4. Reconstructed signal 3, 1st point prediction, 30% unknown patterns, simple input MLP

Figure 5. Reconstructed signal 3, 1st point prediction, 30% unknown patterns, DWT augmented input MLP

Besides, Table 1 reveals the improved convergence capabilities of this network by considering the enhanced minimum sums of squared errors reached during its training phase. The associated training error curves, shown for both MLPs in Figures 6-11, illustrate the efficiency of the proposed DWT augmented input vector MLP concerning convergence speed.

Signal	Input Pattern Type	% unknown patterns	min SSE-test-1 st point ¹	min SSE-test-2 nd point ²	min SSE-training-1 st +2 nd points ³
1 st	32 signal samples	10%	0.35	1.127	0.65
1 st	32 signal samples + 16 DWT coefficients	10%	0.239	1.009	0.63
1 st	32 signal samples	30%	0.551	2.216	0.48
1 st	32 signal samples + 16 DWT coefficients	30%	0.319	1.288	0.46
2 nd	32 signal samples	10%	1.388	4.199	0.36
2 nd	32 signal samples + 16 DWT coefficients	10%	0.821	2.985	0.28
2 nd	32 signal samples	30%	0.327	1.407	0.22
2 nd	32 signal samples + 16 DWT coefficients	30%	0.252	1.311	0.22
3 rd	32 signal samples	10%	1.057	6.319	0.57
3 rd	32 signal samples + 16 DWT coefficients	10%	0.557	3.582	0.48
3 rd	32 signal samples	30%	2.062	8.511	0.47
3 rd	32 signal samples + 16 DWT coefficients	30%	0.371	2.132	0.42

Table 1. The results concerning MLP signal modeling accuracy in both training and test sets for the twelve experiments carried out.

¹ **min SSE-test-1st point** : minimum Sum of Squared Errors reached in the prediction of the first future point in the test set.

² **min SSE-test-2nd point** : minimum Sum of Squared Errors reached in the prediction of the second future point in the test set.

³ **min SSE-training-1st + 2nd points** : minimum Sum of Squared Errors reached in the prediction of both future points in the training set.

Figure 6. Training error curves, signal 1, 10% unknown patterns

Figure 7. Training error curves, signal 1, 30% unknown patterns

Figure 8. Training error curves, signal 2, 10% unknown patterns

Figure 9. Training error curves, signal 2, 30% unknown patterns

Figure 10. Training error curves, signal 3, 10% unknown patterns

Figure 11. Training error curves, signal 3, 30% unknown patterns

Error! Not a valid embedded object.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A new robust method for modeling irregular signals has been presented using the wavelet transform for improved feature extraction. More specifically, the initial vectors containing the signal samples organized in sliding windows, are augmented with suitably selected wavelet coefficients. It is extensively experimentally demonstrated that when the obtained vectors are used as input vectors of function approximators, like MLPs, the result is a significant improvement in both their training and generalization performance, despite the increase in input space dimensionality. These experimental results show the importance of the proposed strategy for enhancing function approximators capabilities by actively seeking for new additional informative features, contrary to the widely accepted approach of reducing model complexity.

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